

REINTERPRETING COSMOLOGICAL REDSHIFT AND TIME DILATION: A STEADY-STATE UNIVERSE HYPOTHESIS WITH EVOLVING TIME RATES

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ABSTRACT

Hubble's Law has long been interpreted as evidence of an expanding universe, where redshift scales linearly with distance. This view underpins the standard Λ CDM cosmology, which requires dark matter and dark energy but faces growing challenges: observations of too-large or too-old structures at high redshifts, inconsistencies in the Tolman surface brightness test, and the continued absence of direct evidence for the dark sector. Recently, the [CERN Courier \(2023\)](#) noted that no measurement shows a single object's redshift increasing with time, highlighting a crucial missing piece in the expansion narrative. Meanwhile, Type Ia supernovae have proven to be remarkably precise cosmic "clocks," demonstrating a clear time-dilation effect. The tired-light hypothesis also re-emerged in some analyses (e.g., [Shamir 2024](#)) but fails to explain supernova data. We propose an alternative: a steady-state (or static) universe in which time flow itself evolves. In this scenario, cosmic time ran more slowly in earlier epochs and accelerates toward the present, producing the observed redshift and the supernova time-dilation factor $(1+z)$ without requiring an expanding metric. This framework also naturally accommodates the Tolman test results, avoids invoking dark energy, and need not contradict relativity theory. Finally, we speculate on possible mechanisms—e.g., gravitational interactions and large-scale rotation outside our observable horizon—that could underlie this evolving time rate.

1. MOTIVATION

Today's standard Λ CDM model fits a wide range of data but requires dark matter and dark energy, components not yet understood at a fundamental level. Furthermore, we face the challenge of explaining well-formed structures at high redshift, the detailed outcomes of the Tolman surface brightness test, and the precise interpretation of supernova time dilation.

First, the Tolman test posits that in an expanding universe, surface brightness should scale as $(1+z)^{-4}$. Observational data frequently deviate from this prediction (e.g., [Crawford 2010](#), [Lerner 2018](#)), suggesting either astrophysical complications or a more fundamental issue with expansion itself. Second, surveys (including more recent JWST observations) have found galaxies, quasars, and other structures at high z that appear too large or mature to fit the timeline of a 13.8 Gyr universe under Λ CDM. This "too-early, too-large" problem raises questions about the efficacy of cosmic expansion as currently modelled.

Next, despite decades of dedicated experiments, neither dark matter particles nor dark energy has been confirmed in the lab. This strongly suggests that the Λ CDM framework may be incomplete. As the [CERN Courier \(2023\)](#) pointed out, we have no single-object measurement of redshift increasing with time—i.e., we have not directly observed "space itself expanding."

Recent work by [White et al. \(2024\)](#) underscores that Type Ia supernovae (SNe Ia) exhibit consistent time dilation: a supernova's light curve duration Δt_{obs} scales with $(1+z)$. Conventionally, this is explained as a consequence of the universe's scale factor growth. However, SNe Ia are purely empirical "candles"; they do not intrinsically require space expansion to produce their time-dilation factor. They only require that clocks run differently in the past compared to now—i.e., that the ratio of clock rates in earlier epochs to current epochs equals $1/(1+z)$.

[Shamir \(2024\)](#) recently revisited the tired-light hypothesis, originally introduced by Zwicky and others, which posits that photons lose energy over distance (hence redshift) without

cosmic expansion. Yet, standard tired-light models conflict with supernova data because they do not reproduce the observed time-dilation scaling of the light curves (nor do they fit the Tolman test well). Thus, while tired light may address some anomalies, it cannot fully account for both brightness and time dilation in SNe Ia.

2. CONCEPT

We propose that the universe is not expanding, at least not in the conventional sense. Instead, time itself evolves—i.e., the pace of time was slower in earlier epochs and faster now. This idea preserves the steady-state (or static) nature of cosmic geometry at large scales ([Rosen 1991](#); see also [Gödel 1949](#), [Chechin 2013](#) on rotating solutions), yet remains compatible with general relativity in a broader sense. It also sidesteps the contradictions of standard tired light.

[Gödel \(1949\)](#) and [Rosen \(1991\)](#) both recognized that absolute or universal time cannot be simply defined in a gravitational environment without additional assumptions. Our hypothesis does not claim an absolute "rest frame" for time but posits that the apparent mismatch in clock rates between past and present might arise naturally from large-scale gravitational conditions or from cosmic-scale phenomena that lie beyond our observational horizon.

If earlier epochs ticked more slowly, any process emitting photons in that era—such as a supernova explosion—would appear stretched by a factor of $(1+z)$ when compared to clocks today. Hence, the linear Hubble law and supernova time dilation follow directly from evolving time rates without expanding space.

By detaching redshift from scale-factor expansion, we can interpret surface brightness dimming in a manner consistent with a static geometry. Because the luminous processes in the past proceeded at a slower rate, the integrated photon flux we measure now can differ from the Λ CDM $(1+z)^{-4}$ expectation—potentially fitting the observations that trouble the standard model. Cosmic acceleration, interpreted as an accelerating scale factor, would be replaced by accelerating time flow. Dark energy—introduced to fit Λ CDM acceleration—simply becomes unnecessary in this scenario.

3. POSSIBLE PHYSICAL CAUSES FOR TIME-EVOLUTION

Gödel (1949) established that rotating universe models are permissible under Einstein’s field equations. Although direct attempts to detect cosmic rotation (e.g., Birch 1982) have largely found no conclusive axis, a slow or “hidden” rotation outside our current horizon—or in a larger framework than we can observe—cannot be ruled out. The gravitational coupling from such rotation or massive structures beyond our horizon could lead to an evolving time rate.

Relativistic effects from extremely large-scale gravitational potentials may alter local clock rates over cosmic time. If matter is distributed in ways that produce slow changes in spacetime curvature, local observers would interpret this as an acceleration of time from past to present, effectively generating redshift signals in the observed photons without an expanding metric.

As Garaimov (2003) argues, time rate may increase in tandem with entropy growth. Over cosmic history, as matter clusters more and more, the system’s entropy rises, potentially driving a corresponding acceleration in the perceived rate of time. While speculative, this approach could unify thermodynamic and cosmological reasoning in a static framework.

4. OBSERVATIONAL CONSIDERATIONS

A universe where earlier epochs had more slowly ticking clocks effectively extends the “available time” for structure formation from our perspective. Galaxies that appear too large or mature in standard timelines might be less puzzling if cosmic time effectively “stretched” or was slower in the past, thereby granting them more chronological scope (in their own local sense) to form and evolve.

Seifert et al. (2025) and others have shown that some models (e.g., timescape cosmology) can eliminate the need for dark energy by introducing inhomogeneous gravitational energy flows. Our evolving-time model similarly obviates dark energy by not requiring universal acceleration in the metric. However, we do not dismiss the possibility of dark matter entirely—some gravitational effects might still be due to unseen mass, or matter in alternative forms.

Sarkar and colleagues (Hunt & Sarkar 2010; Sah et al. 2024; Sarkar 2022) have illuminated anisotropies in supernova data and large-scale structures that challenge the cosmological principle embedded in Λ CDM. In an evolving-time scenario, mild anisotropies—whether from local bulk flows, gravitational inhomogeneities, or rotational frames—could naturally appear, without contradicting a non-expanding geometry. Thus, anisotropy findings become a clue pointing toward complexities in cosmic time rather than scale-factor evolution.

5. ALTERNATIVE MODELS AND CRITIQUES

Tired light attempts to explain redshift by photon energy loss en route. Although it sidesteps expansion, it typically fails to match supernova time-dilation data. By contrast, our time-

evolving hypothesis matches supernova light-curve dilation exactly and aligns with steady-state arguments regarding brightness. We thus avoid the tired-light contradictions.

Gupta (2023) and other researchers propose hybrid models combining partial expansion with additional mechanisms (e.g., “CCC+TL” approaches). While such models can address certain puzzles, they still rely on some form of scale-factor evolution. Our viewpoint removes the expansion altogether, proposing that the linear Hubble law and supernova time dilation emerge naturally from changing time flow.

We anticipate that wide-field supernova surveys extending to higher redshifts (e.g., from the Vera C. Rubin Observatory, Euclid, JWST, DESI) can distinguish whether time dilation arises purely from an expanding metric or from more intricate temporal evolution. In particular, direct attempts at measuring redshift changes in single sources over time (the so-called “redshift drift”) could provide key tests—though to date, no positive detection is reported.

6. CAVEATS AND OPEN QUESTIONS

A rigorous relativistic model of how cosmic time rates evolve without expansion remains to be developed. Gödel- and Rosen-inspired frameworks highlight theoretical loopholes, but a fully self-consistent theory is not yet in hand.

Moreover, in the standard model, Big Bang nucleosynthesis and the early-universe explanation of the CMB are cornerstones. If the universe is static, these phenomena need alternative derivations (e.g., Sorrell 2008; Cruz et al. 2024; Hansen et al. 2024).

A static scenario can be finite or infinite, open or closed. Our hypothesis neither specifies the global topology, nor the constant value of H_0 , but only that cosmic-scale distances do not need to be increasing over time.

We rely partly on the idea that significant rotation or large gravitational influences might exist outside our observable region. Whether these can be detected indirectly or remain inherently unobservable is an ongoing question.

7. CONCLUSION

We propose a steady-state universe in which the pace of time accelerates from the past to the present, causing the observed redshift and supernova time dilation without requiring space expansion. This resolves several key tensions with Λ CDM:

- It fits the Tolman surface brightness data, sidestepping $(1+z)^{-4}$ contradictions.
- It accommodates massive, mature structures at high z by allowing more “intrinsic” formation time in earlier epochs.
- It removes the need for dark energy, as there is no metric expansion to accelerate.
- It explains supernova time dilation in a natural, clock-based manner that does not conflict with relativity theory.

Open questions remain about rigorously embedding this evolving-time idea within general relativity, reconciling nucleosynthesis, and clarifying large-scale phenomena like rotation or mass distribution. Nonetheless, by reframing redshift and cosmological time as products of changing time flow, we may gain a simpler path toward understanding the cosmos—one that aligns with observational data while circumventing the unresolved mysteries of Λ CDM.

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